

Reduction of some flavanones and *E*-3-benzylidene flavanones under modified Clemmensen reduction condition

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Abstract : A mild and efficient method for reduction of flavanones and *E*-3-benzylidene flavanones has been developed by using modified Clemmensen reduction condition [Zn(Hg), CH₃COOH, EtOH, reflux, 1.5 h]. Flavanones gave flavans and *E*-3-benzylidene flavanones gave 3-benzylflavans and 3-benzylflav-3-enes.

Keyword : Flavanone, flavan, *E*-3-benzylidene flavanone, flav-3-ene, modified Clemmensen reduction, de-oxygenation.

Introduction

Synthetic procedures using readily available reagents under mild conditions have lately been receiving much attention from organic chemists. Easy separation of products from the reaction mixtures is a key point in the production of large quantities of organic compounds. Several methods for preparation of flav-3-enes, an important type of intermediates in flavonoid chemistry, are reported in the literature¹⁻⁷. In a recent communication, Hiegel and Carney⁸ reported that arylalkenes could be obtained from arylketones by a modified Clemmensen reduction procedure. Simplicity of this reaction encouraged us to attempt for preparing flav-3-enes from flavanones which can

be synthesised very easily. Again, *E*-3-benzylidene flavanones, directly obtainable either from flavanones or from *o*-hydroxyacetophenones⁹ were also chosen as candidates for the same reduction. The results obtained in the reduction of these two classes of compounds are presented in this paper.

Results and discussion

The reaction of flavanones did not yield the desired arylalkenes (i.e. flav-3-enes), instead, they yielded flavans (Scheme 1) in very good yield (Table 1) by simple de-oxygenation of the starting materials. *E*-3-Benzylidene flavanones (2) yielded a mixture of 3-benzylflavans and 3-benzylflav-3-enes, the former possibly having *trans*

a : R¹ = R² = H; b : R¹ = H, R² = OMe; c : R¹ = Me, R² = Cl

Scheme 1

Table 1. Reduction of flavanones and *E*-3-benzylidene flavanones under modified Clemmensen reduction condition

Starting material	Product	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)
1a	3a	79	Liquid
1b	3b	82	69–70
1c	3c	78	73–74
2a	4a + 5a	68	–
2b	4b + 5b	70	140–141 of 4b

Scheme 2**Table 2.** Results of reduction of **2b** by varying the mole ratio of Zn and HgCl₂

Experiment No.	Reaction condition	Mole ratio of Zn and HgCl ₂	Mole ratio of products 4b and 5b ^a	Combined yield (%)
1.	Zn(Hg), CH ₃ COOH, EtOH, reflux, 1.5 h	60 : 1	2 : 1	66
2.	do	50 : 1	1 : 1	69
3.	do	40 : 1	3 : 2	70
4.	do	30 : 1	1 : 1	64

^aThe mole ratio of the products was determined from ¹H NMR spectral data of the product mixtures.

configuration (Scheme 2). The product ratio was found to be dependent on the mole ratio of Zn and HgCl₂ used for generating Zn-Hg. However, any definite relationship between this mole ratio and product composition could not be observed using compound **2b** as substrate (Table 2). The results of reduction of **2a** and **2b** under a particular reaction condition (vide Experimental) are included in Table 1.

The modified Clemmensen reduction procedure of Hiegel and Carney was comparatively milder than that of the usual Clemmensen reduction procedure. We thought that the arylketones could easily react to form the zinc-carbene intermediates **6** which then underwent rearrange-

ment as the major pathway yielding arylalkenes as major product. On the other hand, formation of arylalkane requires two consecutive protonation reaction of the zinc-carbene complex, which is obviously favoured under strongly acidic condition. Thus, protonation of zinc-carbene complex and its rearrangement could be considered as competitive reactions, and not only the acid strength of the reaction medium but also the nature of the substrate will play remarkable role in determining the composition of the products formed during the course of reaction. It may be assumed here that the zinc-carbene complexes obtained from flavanones favour protonation even under mild acidic condition and this is due to donation of

electron from the ring oxygen (vide 7). Such a process would favour the formation of flavans from flavanones (Scheme 3). Again, from consideration of the reported mechanisms of Clemmensen reduction¹⁰⁻¹², the mechanistic paths shown in Scheme 4 may be delineated for formation of 3-benzylflavans (4) and 3-benzylfav-3-enes (5) from *E*-3-benzylidene flavanones (2).

Scheme 3

Scheme 4

The method of Sanseverino *et al.*¹³ for conversion of olefins to 2-methoxyalkyl iodides by treatment with I₂/MeOH was applied to the mixture of 4b and 5b obtained from reaction of 2b. It was thought that the addition product(s) from 5b would be more polar than 4b and that would make isolation of the latter in pure state by column chromatography possible. As per our anticipation, formation of a more polar product in this reaction was indi-

cated by TLC. However, column chromatography of the resulting mixture over silica gel gave only pure 4b and not any expected addition product.

In conclusion, we have developed a simple and efficient methodology for conversion of flavanones to flavans and *E*-3-benzylidene flavanones to 3-benzylflav-3-enes and 3-benzylflavans.

Typical experimental procedure :

A mixture of zinc dust (0.077 mol), HgCl₂ (0.92 mmol), water (10 ml), and conc. HCl (0.2 ml) was stirred for 10 min and then the liquid was decanted. The lumps of solid so obtained were broken up and to it were added acetic acid (10 ml), 95% ethanol (3 ml) and the starting material (4 mmol). The mixture was refluxed with stirring for 1–1.5 h. The liquid was decanted into a separatory funnel, and residue was stirred with 20 ml of CH₂Cl₂ for 5 min. The residue was washed two more times with 20 ml of CH₂Cl₂ and the CH₂Cl₂ was used to extract the aqueous phase each time. The combined CH₂Cl₂ solution was washed with 1 N NaOH until the wash was basic and saturated with NaCl solution (50 ml) and dried over anhy.

Na₂SO₄. The concentrate of the extract showing one major TLC spot was chromatographed over silica gel to obtain pure product.

3a : ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 60 MHz) : δ 1.75–2.13 (2H, m, H₂-3), 2.60–2.90 (2H, m, H₂-4), 4.92 (1H, dd, *J* 8 and 4.5 Hz, H-2) and 6.66–7.40 (9H, m, Ar-H).

3b : ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 60 MHz) : δ 1.76–2.15 (2H,

m, H₂-3), 2.66–2.95 (2H, m, H₂-4), 3.67 (3H, s, -OCH₃), 4.87 (1H, dd, *J* 8 and 4.5 Hz, H-2), 6.66–7.00 (6H, m, Ar-H) and 7.23 (2H, d, *J* 8 Hz, H-2', 6).

3c : ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 60 MHz) : δ 1.91–2.01 (1H, m, H_A-3), 2.05–2.19 (1H, m, H_B-3), 2.19 (3H, s, -CH₃), 2.62–2.70 (1H, m, H_A-4), 2.82–2.87 (1H, m, H_B-4), 4.93 (1H, dd, *J* 9 and 4 Hz, H-2), 6.76 (1H, d, *J* 7 Hz, H-8), 6.86–6.91 (2H, m, H-5, H-7) and 7.30 (4H, s, H-2', 3', 5', 6').

4a : ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) : δ 2.23–2.57 (5H, m, H-3, H₂-4 and C₆H₅-CH₂-), 4.82 (1H, d, *J* 6 Hz, H-2), 6.33 (1H, d, *J* 3.2 Hz, Ar-H), 6.81 (1H, d, *J* 2.1 Hz, Ar-H), 7.83 (1H, d, *J* 6.9 Hz, Ar-H), 7.23–7.38 (11H, m, Ar-H) (assigned from the ¹H NMR spectrum of the mixture of **4a** and **5a**).

4b : ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) : δ 2.26 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.24–2.60 (5H, m, H-3, H₂-4 and *p*-Cl-C₆H₄-CH₂-), 4.80 (1H, d, *J* 6.6 Hz, H-2), 6.77 (1H, d, *J* 1.5 Hz, H-5), 6.79 (1H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz, H-8), 6.93 (1H, dd, *J* 8.4 and 1.5 Hz, H-7), 7.01 (2H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz, H-2'', 6'') and 7.21–7.36 (6H, Ar-H).

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